

The Effects of Prospective Memory Load on Decision Making Outcomes

A Preliminary Study

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Decision making (DM) is a process that we go through on a daily basis. In the process of making decisions, we often have to contemplate various factors while having to remember various other things for the day such as appointments with other people and remembering to pick up specific groceries. This backdrop of things to remember is a process supported by prospective memory (PM). While individually, DM and PM have been studied extensively, the interaction between the 2 neural processes has not been examined in depth. This study aims to fill this gap.

METHODS: The Cups Task from a previous experiment on decision making is merged with prospective memory tasks of different memory loads to study the impact of the load on the reaction times and risk rates of the decision making tasks.

RESULTS: There were no significant results ($p = .05$) in an analysis using 3-way repeated ANOVA. Significant results were obtained ($p < .05$) after adjusting for response bias using the d' statistic suggesting differences in the risk rates for decision making between prospective memory loads.

CONCLUSION: The experiment demonstrates that the new paradigm is suitable for investigating the impact of prospective memory loads on decision making although response bias is present. The results support the hypothesis that prospective memory load alters risk taking behaviour of the subjects.

Keywords: prospective memory, decision making

1 Introduction

Decision making (DM) is a process that we go through on a daily basis. In the process of making decisions, we often have to contemplate various factors influencing the decision. This process is often done while having to remember various other things for the day such as appointments with other people and remembering to pick up specific groceries. This backdrop of things to remember is a process supported by prospective memory (PM). While individually, DM and PM have been studied extensively, the interaction between the 2 neural processes has not been examined in depth.

1.1 Decision making

While there are many different forms of decisions that we make on a daily basis, decisions with an element of risk are of great interest to researchers as such decisions can have serious implications or consequences. Recent studies which focused on DM with explicit risks have found different sensitivity towards gaining and losing rewards (Weller et al., 2007; Xue et al., 2009) as supported by previous findings that suggest that humans' response to negative events differ from positive events (Baumeister et al., 2001; Kahneman & Tversky, 1979; Levin et al., 1998).

Studies on DM have also found heavy involvement of executive functions in different stages of decision making with activations of brain regions such as the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex during valuation (Labudda et al., 2008) and the Brodmann area 10 (medial frontal gyrus) during evaluation of risks (Lawrence et al., 2009).

These studies of DM use a single type of task (e.g. Iowa Gambling Task, Game of Dice Task etc.) to determine the subjects' risk behaviour under the win and lose domain, however, in real life, we often encounter decisions while having multiple delayed intentions in their minds. Hence, this study aims to modify the original paradigm to make it ecologically more plausible by incorporating PM tasks.

1.1.1 Conceptual model for DM

A conceptual model (Figure 1) is used to frame the components of DM. A review of the different models revealed 5 major stages in DM, namely: sensory input (Gold & Shadlen, 2007; Sugrue et al., 2005), valuation of input, selection of competing possibilities, execution of action (Ernst & Paulus, 2005; Gold & Shadlen, 2007; Kable & Glimcher, 2009; Sugrue et al., 2005) and receiving feedback from the outcome (Ernst & Paulus, 2005; Gold & Shadlen, 2007; Sugrue et al., 2005). All of these stages occur sequentially with the last stage feeding back information to the loop thus allowing the respondent to revise the valuation of the input.

1.2 Prospective memory

PM is defined as a memory which holds the information for a future action (Einstein & McDaniel, 1995). An important feature of PM is the existence of the intention superiority effect (ISE) (Goschke & Kuhl, 1993) which improves accessibility of the information encoded for delayed execution (Marsh et al., 1998). It is related to other cognitive functions such as attention (Altmann & Trafton, 2002; Freeman & Ellis, 2003) and prefrontal executive functions (Shallice & Burgess, 1991). Another important feature of PM is the ability to switch attention from stimulus-independent (during delay before execution) to

Figure 1: Conceptual model of DM.

stimulus-oriented (during execution of task) while maintaining the intention in memory all this while. The process is largely mediated by the Brodmann area 10 (Burgess et al., 2007).

Like DM, there are various forms of PM such as time-based (Einstein & McDaniel, 1990; Kvavilashvili & Ellis, 1995; Zimmer et al., 2007), activity-based (Kvavilashvili & Ellis, 1995), event-based (Einstein & McDaniel, 1990; Zimmer et al., 2007) and cue-based (Kvavilashvili & Ellis, 1995; Zimmer et al., 2007). While differences between the various forms exist, they share an underlying trait which is that it is a form of memory for delayed intentions waiting to be realised (Ellis, 1995).

To better define the construct of PM, a conceptual model that is applicable for the different forms of PM would be used.

1.2.1 Conceptual model for PM

A review of various models revealed 5 main stages in the formation and use of PM (Figure 2) (Einstein & McDaniel, 1995; Ellis, 1995; Zimmer, 2001; Zimmer et al., 2007). The period of delay is a period whereby the memory system is awaiting a cue, event, activity etc. is dependent on the form of PM that is being used. In a scenario whereby the cue, event or activity is not being recognised, the person may choose to re-encode the task as a follow-up.

1.3 Decision making with prospective memory

As outlined earlier in the conceptual models for DM and PM, both of these processes involve achieving a specific goal. In the case of DM, it is to make the most beneficial choice given the existing information and in the case of PM, it is to successfully execute a delayed intention. Goal orientation has been found

Figure 2: Conceptual model of stages in the formation and use of PM.

to tap primarily on the cortico-striatal network which involves areas such as the medial prefrontal cortex and the anterior cingulate cortex (Balleine et al., 2008). The neural substrates involved in DM and PM as mentioned previously have overlaps with these areas.

Furthermore, the overlaps in several other stages such as evaluation of the execution of a task based on a criterion held in the memory and the evaluation of an outcome suggests that the 2 processes are tightly intertwined when conducted simultaneously.

Also, a key neural substrate involved in the use of PM, Brodmann area 10, is also involved in DM. The overlaps in the neural substrates involved in each process suggest that attention has to shift from one task to another during each task switch. The effects of this switch on both DM and PM are uncertain.

Given the multiple overlaps in processes and neural substrates and the frequent presentation of the 2 processes in tandem in our daily lives, the interaction between the 2 processes needs to be explored further. This exploration would require both the processes to be present and the presence of only one of them would not offer a complete picture of the underlying interactions.

1.4 Hypothesis

Based on the above, there are many processes and neural substrates that are shared by both DM and PM. Given that the 2 processes are often done simultaneously, it would therefore be useful to know how the 2 processes when executed in parallel, affect each other. The hypothesis for the study is therefore:

1. The risk rates for DM tasks would change with increased PM load although the direction of change is unclear as the 2 processes share similar underlying supporting processes and neural substrates and hence their simultaneous usage of the available cognitive resources would bring about changes to the decision making behaviour.

2. The risk rates for DM tasks grouped by risk condition in descending order is risk advantageous, equal expected value and risk disadvantageous. This is a logical sequence of risk taking tendency and has been verified in previous experiments employing the Cups Task.
3. Risk rates for the lose domain are lower than the risk rates for the win domain as the subjects would be expected to be more conservative in the lose domains when compared to the win domains which is explained in the introduction on decision making.
4. The response time across the conditions would not be significantly different as there is no evidence to suggest that the reaction time is expected to be different across the different conditions.
5. The PM accuracy rate and no response proportion would be significantly related to the risk rates. This is under the premise that when a subject fails to respond to a DM task or answers a PM task incorrectly, the subject would have more available resources to cope with evaluation of the risks.

2 Methods

2.1 Experimental paradigm

The experimental paradigm employs a block design. Within each block, one level of PM and all levels of DM conditions would be employed. The design would be discussed in more detail in subsequent sections.

2.1.1 The Cups Task

The experimental paradigm used is adapted from the Cups Task (Weller et al., 2007; Xue et al., 2009). The Cups Task is a computerised DM paradigm aimed at exploring the risk taking behaviour of the subjects when faced with different risk conditions (risk advantageous, risk disadvantageous and equal expected value) in winning and losing monetary rewards (win/lose domains). In the Cups Task, 2 sets of cups with varying amounts of reward displayed on top are presented to the subject as shown in Figure 3 and the subject would need to choose either the left or right set of cups represented by a left and right button within 2.5 seconds.

Figure 3: DM task.

The risk condition would not be explicitly expressed but can be deduced from the number of cups and reward while the win/lose domain is indicated by a “+” or “-” sign to represent a win or lose task respectively.

In all the DM tasks, there would be a set of cups representing the safe option and a set of cups representing the risky option. In the example in Figure 3, the left side is the safe option and the right side is the risky option. The “+\$1” on top of 1 cup which represents the safe option means that the \$1 indicated on top is contained in the cup. Therefore, there is a 100% chance of getting the \$1 if this option is chosen. Likewise for the risky option, the “+\$3” on top of the 3 cups represent a 1 out of 3 chance in winning the \$3. If the risky option is chosen, 1 out of the 3 cups would be automatically chosen and the outcome (either win \$3 or win \$0) would be shown to the subject.

The risk condition is determined by the expected value of the risky option which is computed by multiplying the reward and the probability of receiving the reward. As all the DM tasks would have a safe option with an expected value of 1, this would be used as a reference to determine if the DM task is risk advantageous, disadvantageous or equal expected value. Table 1 outlines the different expected value for the 6 conditions for the DM tasks.

Table 1: Expected value of risk conditions.

Expected value	Risk advantageous		Risk disadvantageous		Equal expected value	
	Win	Lose	Win	Lose	Win	Lose
	> 1	< -1	< 1	> -1	1	-1

The aim for the subject is to win as much money as possible in the win domain and lose as little money as possible in the lose domain.

2.1.2 Prospective memory tasks

PM tasks are interspersed in between 6–9 DM tasks. The PM tasks consist of cups that are of different colours (versus blue cups only in the DM task) as shown in Figure 4. Like the DM tasks, the subject would need to choose to press either the left or right button within 2.5 seconds. The choice would depend on the rule taught to the subject before the start of the block of experiment. 2 levels of PM, low and high, are created to simulate different loads on the PM. The 2 levels differ in the number of steps required to complete the analysis of the stimulus before making a decision as suggested by Ellis (1995). The rules are outlined in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Of note is that the subjects would not receive feedback on the outcome of their choice. This is done to prevent the subject from adding additional prospective memory tasks after giving a wrong answer as the additional tasks may create different levels of prospective memory load.

2.1.3 Block design

6 different blocks are used for the study as shown in Table 2. In block 3 and 5, the subject is asked to ignore the PM tasks. This serves as a baseline DM response. Although blocks 3 and 5 are theoretically no different from each other, to ensure that the presence of different PM tasks do not affect their DM characteristics, they are still carried out. In blocks 4 and 6, the subject is asked to ignore the DM tasks, thus forming the baseline response for the PM tasks.

For each block of DM tasks, the subject is exposed to 6 different conditions. Table 3 summarises the breakdown of number of tasks in each DM tasks block.

Figure 4: PM tasks interspersed between DM tasks.

Figure 5: Low load PM task response rule.

Table 2: Block characteristics.

Block	No. of DM tasks	No. of PM tasks	PM load used
1	176	24	Low
2	176	24	High
3	176	0	Low
4	0	24	Low
5	176	0	High
6	0	24	High

Figure 6: High load PM task response rule.

Table 3: Breakdown of number of DM tasks.

Risk condition	Win/lose	Number of tasks
RA	Win	32
RA	Lose	32
RD	Win	32
RD	Lose	32
EQEV	Win	24
EQEV	Lose	24
Total		176

RA = risk advantageous; RD = risk disadvantageous; EQEV = equal expected value

The Latin square was used to reorder the blocks to negate the order effects of the design. The different order of blocks used is summarised in Table 4. The subjects were randomly assigned an order. The subjects were allowed to rest for up to 10 minutes once at a time of their own choosing in between the blocks.

Table 4: Order of blocks.

Order	Order of blocks
1	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6
2	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 1
3	3, 4, 5, 6, 1, 2
4	4, 5, 6, 1, 2, 3
5	5, 6, 1, 2, 3, 4
6	6, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5

2.2 Pilot study

Prior to the pilot study, amendments were made to the experimental paradigm to ensure that various parameters (frequency of coloured cups appearing on each side, left or right response, tasks that require different rules) are well balanced. Instructions were standardised and a cash reward system was created.

The reward system consists of a fixed cash reward and a varying bonus dependent on the subject's performance on the DM and PM task. The amount of the subject's winnings on the DM task that is more than the fixed cash reward is the bonus. The subject would be eligible to this bonus only if they had scored at least 80% correct for the PM tasks. This is done to ensure that the subjects put in reasonable effort in both the DM and PM tasks.

4 subjects were recruited for the pilot study. Initial findings supported the hypothesis that the presence of PM tasks affected risk taking behaviours. Additionally, it was found that there were latent rules that can be applied to the high level PM tasks that allow circumvention of the prescribed rules. The PM tasks were modified to ensure that in the event that these latent rules are discovered, they will not be applicable all the time. The pilot study was also used to sort out operational issues in administering the experiment.

After the pilot study, some improvements were made to the conducting of the study. A training programme was created to build up proficiency in the PM tasks for the subjects prior to attempting the actual experimental stimulus. A threshold of 90% correct was set as the required proficiency.

2.3 Subjects

Subjects were sampled from the Hong Kong Polytechnic University. They consist of existing students aged 19–25 studying in Hong Kong Polytechnic with no history of neurological deficits. The decision to use normal subjects instead of subjects with known neurological deficits is because the Cups Task is a relatively new experimental paradigm and the profile of the performance from people with different neurological deficits has not been established. Furthermore, modifications were made to the Cups Task to include prospective memory tasks and hence the need to establish a baseline performance on a normal population. Also, the accessible sample was limited to students from the university due to a lack of other formal contacts in recruitment of subjects.

Ethics approval from the Hong Kong Polytechnic University was obtained prior to the recruitment of subjects. Information about the study was disseminated via email. Informed consent was obtained before the commencement of any data collection.

2.4 Data collection

Data was collected using the computerised experimental paradigm. After each subject has completed all 6 blocks of the experiment, the set of raw data would be processed using R (The R Development Core Team, 2010) to generate the mean of each subject for each condition. The variables of interests are the risk rate and response time for the DM tasks and accuracy and response time for the PM tasks. Additionally, the no response rate for both the DM and PM tasks were generated.

2.5 Data analysis

The data is analysed using 3 methods. The first method uses the attention operating characteristic (AOC) curves (Sperling & Melchner, 1978) to determine the relationship between the risk rates of the various conditions with the accuracy of the PM tasks.

The second method uses a 3-way repeated measure ANOVA model with the PM levels, risk condition and win or lose task as the 3 factors of interest. The measures used are the response time and risk rate. The analysis was conducted using SPSS Statistics 18.0 (SPSS Inc., an IBM Company, 2010).

The third method is to compute the d' (Green & Swets, 1989; Wickens, 2002) for each level of PM across the win and lose domains. The d' is used as the subjects may prefer to continually make risky choices without consideration of the risk condition. Hence, the d' would be used to negate the effects of such response bias. In the case of the experiment, the d' would be computed using the following formula:

$$d' = z(\text{Risk rate for risk advantageous}) - z(\text{Risk rate for risk disadvantageous})$$

Where applicable, the risk rates are adjusted by 1×10^{-8} to allow computation of the z-score.

3 Results and analysis

3.1 Subjects

A total of 24 subjects were recruited for this study. A summary of their demographics can be found in Table 5. The demographics were subsequently used as covariates in the 3-way repeated measure ANOVA but were found to be non-significant and hence were not included in subsequent analysis.

3.2 No response

The no response rate is as summarised in Table 6 and Table 7 respectively for DM and PM tasks. The mean overall no response rate for both DM and PM tasks are low at less than 5% of the total tasks. This indicates that the subjects have placed considerable efforts in responding to the tasks.

Table 5: Demographics of subjects.

Age	Mean (SD)	21.75 (1.42)
	Range	19–25
Gender	Male	9
	Female	15
Years of education	Mean (SD)	15.92 (1.06)
	Range	14–18

Table 6: No response rate for DM tasks (%).

With no PM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.284 (0.410)
	Range	0–1.136
With low level PM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.237 (0.709)
	Range	0–3.409
With high level PM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.166 (0.313)
	Range	0–1.136

Table 7: No response rate for PM tasks (%).

Low level PM tasks with no DM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.347 (1.176)
	Range	0–4.167
High level PM tasks with no DM tasks	Mean (SD)	2.604 (2.962)
	Range	0–8.333
Low level PM tasks with DM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.868 (1.729)
	Range	0–4.167
High level PM tasks with DM tasks	Mean (SD)	3.125 (5.664)
	Range	0–16.667

3.3 Prospective memory tasks accuracy rate

The results for the PM accuracy rate are summarised in Table 8. The mean accuracy rate is above 80%, further supporting that the subjects made considerable effort in responding to the tasks.

Table 8: Accuracy rate for PM tasks.

Low level PM tasks with no DM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.898 (0.030)
	Range	0.833–0.958
High level PM tasks with no DM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.951 (0.052)
	Range	0.792–1.000
Low level PM tasks with DM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.870 (0.069)
	Range	0.625–0.917
High level PM tasks with DM tasks	Mean (SD)	0.944 (0.092)
	Range	0.625–1.000

3.4 Attention operator characteristics – DM risk rate versus PM accuracy rate

The DM risk rate was plotted against the PM accuracy rate for the 3 different risk conditions in both the win and lose domain in (Figure 7 to Figure 12). The baseline DM is the DM risk rate without the PM tasks and the baseline PM is the PM accuracy for each respective PM level.

Figure 7: Risk advantageous, win domain.

3 notable observations were made. Firstly, the AOC curves consistently showed that the PM accuracy decreases across all conditions when done with DM tasks. Secondly, the risk rate for the DM tasks consistently increased across all risk conditions in the win domain and decreased in the lose domain with the introduction of PM tasks. Thirdly, the accuracy rate for the low level PM is consistently lower than that of the high level.

Figure 8: Risk advantageous, lose domain.

Figure 9: Risk disadvantageous, win domain.

Figure 10: Risk disadvantageous, lose domain.

Figure 11: Equal expected value, win domain.

Figure 12: Equal expected value, lose domain.

3.5 3-way repeated measure ANOVA

A 3-way repeated measure ANOVA was conducted using PM levels, risk conditions and win/lose domain as the factors with the risk rate and response times as the outcome measures. The covariates used were the no response rates for both DM and PM across conditions and the PM accuracy rates. Some of the covariates were significant for the 3 factors. As the significance was not uniform across the 3 factors, the covariates are not removed to maintain uniformity in the analysis.

The results of the multivariate tests are summarised in Table 9. All 3 factors were non-significant for risk rate and response time.

Table 9: Statistical test for risk rates and response time.

Hotelling's Trace	F	Significance
PM levels	$F(4, 36) = 1.277$.297
Risk condition	$F(4, 36) = 0.657$.626
Win/Lose domain	$F(2, 9) = 2.963$.103

From the within subject contrasts, the risk rates for DM tasks with high level PM was borderline significantly different from the DM tasks without PM tasks ($p = .052$). No other significant relationships were found.

3.6 d'

The d' is computed and compared across the PM levels and win/lose domains using 2-way repeated measure ANOVA. The results are summarised in Table 10. The d' versus PM accuracy curves was also drawn (Figure 13 and Figure 14).

Table 10: Statistical test for d' .

Hotelling's Trace	F	Significance
PM levels	$F(2, 22) = 5.459$.012
Win/Lose domain	$F(1, 23) = 0.598$.447

Figure 13: d' versus PM accuracy, win domain.

Figure 14: d' versus PM accuracy, lose domain.

The d' is significantly different across the PM levels. Looking at the within subjects contrasts, the d' for DM without PM was significantly different from DM with low and high level PM ($p < .05$). However, the d' for DM with low level PM was not significantly different from the d' for DM with high level PM.

4 Discussion

The 5 hypotheses mentioned in earlier sections would be discussed to assess if the experimental evidence supports the proposed hypothesis or the null hypothesis.

4.1 Hypothesis 1

From the results, we can see that there are consistent differences in risk rates among the different conditions as evident from the AOC curves although the differences are not statistically significant. This result partially supports hypothesis 1 and shed light on the likely relationship between risk rates with PM loads.

One possible reason for the lack of statistical significance could be that the observed power was low. This is likely due to the small sample size obtained. Another possible reason is that there might be inherent inadequacies in the experimental design.

The original proposed 2 levels of PM might not be performing as expected as the high level PM with DM is consistently showing higher levels of accuracies compared to the low level PM with DM. This is despite the fact that the high level PM involves more mental steps to interpret and make a response to the stimulus than the low level PM. This higher level of accuracy might be explained by the presence of a latent rule in the high level PM tasks that renders it easier than the low level PM task. While steps were taken to ensure that this latent rule is not applicable all the time, the steps taken might not have been sufficient to reduce its impact on the performance of the tasks.

Another possible source of confounding factor is response bias. This happens when subjects adopt a certain response (risk/no risk) across trials without seriously considering the risk condition. Response bias could prevent the results from reaching statistical significance. To take into account the response bias, the d' is used as a more reliable indicator.

The d' results support hypothesis 1 and are able to reach statistical significance. It differs from the 3-way repeated measures ANOVA, suggesting that response bias was indeed present in the data collected. The d' contrasts revealed that there were no differences between the 2 PM levels giving further evidence that the 2 levels may not be performing as expected.

4.2 Hypothesis 2

The results from the 3-way repeated measures ANOVA do not support hypothesis 2. As the power of the factor is low, it is possible that real differences exist, but is unable to reach statistical significance.

4.3 Hypothesis 3

Similar to hypothesis 2, 3-way repeated measures ANOVA do not support hypothesis 3 due to a low power. When the analysis for the win/lose domain is run again for the d' statistic, the difference is still

not significant. The power in the d' statistic for the win/lose domain is also low, confirming the previous reasons for lack of significance.

4.4 Hypothesis 4

The 3-way repeated measures ANOVA supports hypothesis 4 as it did not find any significant differences between the response time of the DM tasks across the different conditions.

4.5 Hypothesis 5

The use of PM accuracy rate and no response proportion as covariates in the 3-way repeated measure ANOVA which showed significant results provided some support for hypothesis 5 although the relationship between the PM accuracy rate and no response proportion is not uniform across the different conditions.

4.6 Future improvements

There are 2 main improvements that can be made to the study. Firstly, the sample size should be increased for future studies to ensure adequate power in the analysis. Secondly, the PM levels needs to be revised to ensure that there are no latent rules available for use.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the study has demonstrated the use of a new paradigm to elicit the effects of PM load on risk taking behaviour. The results support hypothesis 1, which suggests that PM levels alter the risk taking behaviour, hypothesis 4, which suggests that the response time is similar across the different conditions and partially support hypothesis 5 which suggests that the no response proportion and PM accuracy rate are related to the DM risk rates.

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